

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

MICROWAVE CHEMISTRY: A REVIEW**Mr. Visal C.S *, Dr. Prasobh G.R., Mrs. Sheeja Rekha A.G, Mr. Nishad V. M,
Mrs. Padmaja Devi M.S**Sreekrishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Parassala, Thiruvananthapuram Dist,
Kerala**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract**

Microwave irradiation provides an alternative to the conventional methods, for heating or introducing energy into the system. It utilizes the ability of mobile electric charges present in liquid or conducting ions in solid to transform electromagnetic energy into heat. Microwave-assisted reactions are fast, clean, economic and eco-friendly and this technique has been proposed as the "technology of tomorrow". The use of microwave irradiation in chemistry has become a popular technique that it might be assumed that, in a few years, most chemists will probably use microwave energy to heat chemical reactions on a laboratory scale. Many scientists, both in academia and in industry, have turned to microwave synthesis as a frontline methodology for their projects. This review highlights applications of microwave chemistry in organic synthesis.

Keywords Microwave, Applications**Corresponding author:****Mr. Visal C.S ***,

Assitant Professor,

Sree Krishna College of Pharmacy and Research Centre,

Parassala, Trivandram Kerala, India 695502

Email: cvisual5@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Visal C.S et al, *Microwave Chemistry: A Review.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020;
07(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Microwave assisted organic synthesis has revolutionized organic synthesis. Small molecules can be built in a fraction of the time required by classical thermal methods. As a result, this technique has rapidly gained acceptance as a valuable tool for accelerating drug discovery and development processes. A microwave is a form of electromagnetic energy, which falls at the lower end of the electromagnetic spectrum and is defined in a measurement of frequency as 300 to 300,000 Megahertz, corresponding to wavelengths of 1 cm to 1m. The microwave region of the electromagnetic spectrum lies between infrared and radiofrequencies^{2,3}. Wavelengths between 1 cm and 25 cm are extensively used for RADAR transmissions and remaining wavelength range is used for telecommunications. In order to avoid interference with radar and telecommunication activities, which also operate in this region, most commercial and domestic microwave ovens operate at 2450 MHz (12.25cm).^[1,2]

The difference between microwave energy another forms of radiation, such as X- and γ -rays, is that microwave energy is non-ionizing and therefore does not alter the molecular structure of the compounds being heated – it provides only thermal activation. The heating effect utilized in microwave assisted organic transformations is mainly due to dielectric polarization. When a molecule is irradiated with microwaves, it aligns itself with the applied field. The rapidly changing electric field (2.45×10^9 Hz) affects the molecule and consequently the molecule continually attempts to align itself with the changing field and energy is absorbed. The ability of a material to convert electromagnetic energy into thermal energy is dependent on the dielectric constant. The larger the dielectric constant the greater is the coupling with microwaves. Thus, solvents such as water, methanol, DMF, ethyl acetate, acetone, acetic acid, etc. are all heated rapidly when irradiated with microwaves.^[3,4] However, solvents with low dielectric constants such as hexane, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, etc. do not couple and therefore do not heat that rapidly under microwave irradiation. Microwave heating has thus been found to be a very convenient thermal source not only in the kitchen but also in a chemical laboratory. Chemists have explored the possibility of the application of a conventional microwave oven to carryout chemical reactions. It has been found that many reactions progress much faster upon microwave irradiation than with traditional heating techniques. The application of microwave irradiation to activate and accelerate organic reactions has taken a new dimension and has experienced exponential growth

in the last ten years. Microwave chemistry is becoming increasingly popular both in industry and in academia. We hope to demonstrate in this article the utility of this technique, and the potential that this methodology can give to the bench chemist.

Microwave Heating

Microwave dielectric heating uses the ability of some liquids and solids to transform electromagnetic radiation into heat to drive chemical reactions. However, the advantages of using microwave dielectric heating for performing organic transformations have only emerged since the mid-1980s. This technology opens up new opportunities to the synthetic chemist, in the form of new reactions that are not possible using conventional heating. Developments in this field have suggested that microwave-assisted chemistry could be used in most reactions that require heating. ^[5,6]

Advantages

In the past, microwave chemistry was often used only when all other options to perform a particular reaction had failed, or when exceedingly long reaction times or high temperatures were required to complete a reaction. This practice is now slowly changing and, due to the growing availability of microwave reactors in many laboratories, routine synthetic transformations are now also being carried out by microwave heating.

Microwave include following advantages, over the conventional heating.

- Uniform heating occurs throughout the material
- Process speed is increased
- High efficiency of heating
- Reduction in unwanted side reaction
- Purity in final product, Improve reproducibility
- Environmental heat loss can be avoided
- Reduce wastage of heating reaction vessel
- Low operating cost^[7,8]

Mechanism

Three main mechanisms are involved for their heating

Dipolar polarization

Polar molecules are the ideal material for dipolar polarization method. On exposure to an oscillating electromagnetic field of appropriate frequency, polar molecules try to follow the field and align themselves in phase with the field. However, owing to inter-molecular forces, polar molecules experience inertia and are unable to follow the field. This results in the random motion of particles, which in turn generates heat. Dipolar polarization can generate heat by either one or both the following mechanisms: Interaction between polar solvent molecules such as water, methanol

and ethanol. Interaction between polar solute molecules such as ammonia and formic acid. The key requirement for dipolar polarization is that the frequency range of the oscillating field should be appropriate to enable adequate inter-particle interaction. If the frequency range is very high, inter-molecular forces will stop the motion of a polar molecule before it tries to follow the field, resulting in inadequate inter-particle interaction. On the other hand, if the frequency range is low, the polar molecule gets sufficient time to align itself in phase with the field. Hence, no random interaction takes place between the adjoining particles. Microwave radiation has the appropriate frequency (0.3-30 GHz) to oscillate polar particles and enable enough inter-particle interaction. This makes it an ideal choice for heating polar solutions. In addition, the energy in a microwave photon (0.037 kcal/mol) is very low, relative to the typical energy required to break a molecular bond (80-120 kcal/mol). Therefore, microwave excitation of molecules does not affect the structure of an organic molecule and the interaction is purely kinetic. [9,10]

Conduction mechanism

The conduction mechanism generates heat through resistance to an electric current. The oscillating electromagnetic field generates an oscillation of electrons or ions in a conductor, resulting in an electric current. This current face internal resistance, which heats the conductor. Major limitation of the method is that it is not applicable for materials with high conductivity; since such materials reflect most of the energy that falls on them. [11,12]

Interfacial polarization

The interfacial polarization method can be considered as a combination of the conduction and dipolar polarization mechanisms. It is important for heating systems that comprise a conducting material dispersed in a non-conducting material. For example, consider the dispersion of metal particles in sulphur. Sulphur does not respond to microwaves and metals reflect most of the microwave energy they are exposed to, but combining the two makes them a good microwave-absorbing material. However, for this to take place, metals have to be used in powder form. This is because, unlike a metal surface, metal powder is a good absorber of microwave radiation. It absorbs radiation and is heated by a mechanism that is similar to dipolar polarization. The environment of the metal powder acts as a solvent for polar molecules and restricts the motion of ions by forces that are equivalent to inter-particle interactions in polar solvents. These restricting forces under the effect of an oscillating field induce a phase lag in

the motion of ions, resulting in random motion of ions and ultimately heating of the system. [13,14]

Applications of Microwave Chemistry

Microwave chemistry is applicable in various industries such as the biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, petroleum, plastics, chemicals etc and major applications have been developed in the field of analytical chemistry and chemical synthesis. Due to the success full development of commercial instrumentation, microwave dielectric heating is now being increasingly applied in chemical reactions. However, most of these applications have been limited to small-scale use in laboratories and have not been extended to the production level. [15,16]

The major industrial applications of microwave chemistry can be segmented as:

1.Applications in Analytical Chemistry

The various applications of microwave radiation in analytical chemistry are:

1.1. Ashing

Ashing is used in various analytical laboratories to determine the ash content in a sample, for the purpose of process and quality control. Microwave heating is extensively used for ashing in the petroleum and fuels, plastics, pharmaceuticals and food industries. In most of these industries, microwave-powered muffle furnaces, which are specifically meant for laboratory use, are used for ashing. These microwave muffle furnaces have proven to be more efficient (about 97%) compared to conventional muffle furnaces. They can reach high temperatures ranging between 1,000 °C and 1,200 °C and can also process a large number of samples simultaneously. [17,18]

1.2. Digestion

Digestion is the process by which samples are broken down to their basic constituents for chemical analysis. Microwave digestion systems are used in analytical laboratories for sample decomposition and preparation. It involves the heating of microwave-absorbing reagents inside a pressurized, microwave-transparent container, in contrast to conventional open vessel digestion. Pressurization allows higher temperatures to be achieved in short period and it increases the speed of digestion. Rapid heating accelerates the reaction rate exponentially and results in an approximately 100-fold decrease in the time required for the process of digestion at 175 °C, compared to such a process conducted at 95 °C. Microwave radiation has now become the technology of choice for sample preparation trace and ultra-trace metals analysis and is being used in the digestion of even the toughest 32organic or inorganic samples in diverse industries. [19,20,21]

1.3 Extraction

Microwave extraction has proved to be more effective and efficient than its conventional counterpart, the Soxhlet extraction method. The Soxhlet extraction, which is a standard technique, is a continuous solvent extraction method. Extraction systems are used to conduct routine solvent extractions of soils, sediments, sludge, polymers and plastics, pulp and paper, biological tissues, textiles and food samples. Experiments have proved that microwaves, in comparison with the Soxhlet extraction, use a lesser volume of solvent and sample and perform extraction at a much faster rate. For example, it has been observed that about 500 microwave extractions can be performed for a given solvent, compared to just 32 Soxhlet extractions. [22,23]

1.4 Moisture analysis

Application of microwave assisted moisture analysis has been extended to food and beverage, chemical, environmental, organic and pharmaceutical industries and has been found to be highly effective in reducing testing time. Microwave moisture analysis is specifically applied at product development stages such as process and quality control, testing of raw materials, intermediate and finished products.

2. Applications in Chemical Synthesis

Application of microwave radiation in chemical synthesis encompasses its use in the acceleration of chemical synthesis. Microwave-enhanced synthesis allows organic chemists to work faster, generate higher yields, and increase product purity. In addition, due to the availability of high-capacity microwave apparatus, the yields of the experiments have now easily scaled up from milligrams to kilograms, without the need to alter reaction parameters. Microwave organic synthesis is the main component of microwave-assisted chemical synthesis. [24,25,26]

2.1 Organic synthesis

Organic synthesis is the preparation of a desired organic compound from available starting materials. Microwave-assisted organic synthesis has been the one of the most researched applications of microwaves in chemical reactions. Chemists have successfully conducted a large range of organic reactions.

These include :

1. Diels-Alder reaction
2. Heck reaction
3. Suzuki reaction
4. Mannich reaction
5. Hydrogenation of [beta]-lactams
6. Hydrolysis
7. Dehydration
8. Esterification
9. Cycloaddition reaction
10. Epoxidation
11. Reductions
12. Condensations

13. Protection and deprotection

14. Cyclisation reactions.

Microwave-assisted organic synthesis is being widely applied in the pharmaceuticals industry, particularly for developing compounds in the lead optimization phase of drug development. In this phase, chemists use diverse synthetic techniques to develop candidate drugs from lead compounds. [27,28,29]

Based on reaction conditions, organic synthesis reactions can be conducted in the following ways:

2.1.1. Organic synthesis at atmospheric pressure

Microwave-assisted organic reactions can be conveniently conducted at atmospheric pressure in reflux conditions e.g. Diels-Alder reaction of maleic anhydride with anthracene. In the presence of diglyme (boiling point 162 °C), this reaction can be completed in a minute, with a 90% yield. However, the conventional synthetic route, which uses benzene, requires 90 minutes. High boiling solvents are preferred in microwave-assisted organic synthetic reactions.

2.1.2 Organic synthesis at elevated pressure

Microwaves can be used to directly heat the solvent in sealed microwave-transparent containers. The sealed container helps in increasing the pressure in the reactor, which facilitates the reaction that will take place at much higher temperatures. This results in a substantial increase in the reaction rate of microwave-assisted organic. However, increase in the reaction rate of any chemical synthesis depends on three factors: volume of the vessel, the solvent to space ratio, and the solvent boiling point.

2.1.2. Organic synthesis in dry media

Microwaves have been applied to organic synthesis in dry media, using solid supports (i.e. alumina, montmorillonite clay, alkali metal fluoride doped alumina and silica.) Microwave radiation, based on solid supports, has been highly successful in reducing the reaction time for condensation, acetylation and deacetylation reactions, for example, deacetylation of a protected compound such as alcoholic acetate held on a support material. The microwave-assisted reaction could be completed within two to three minutes, compared to conventional oil-bath heating at 75 °C for 40 hours.

2.2 Inorganic synthesis

2.2.1. Synthesis of organometallic and coordination compounds

Microwave radiation has been successful in accelerating the reaction rate for the generation of organometallic and coordination compounds, which are produced by generating covalent bonds between organic compounds and metals.

2.2.2. Synthesis of intercalation compounds

Applications of microwave chemistry for intercalation compounds have been tested recently.

Intercalation compounds comprise organic or organometallic compounds that are incorporated between layers of oxides and sulphides. Conventional heating methods for the preparation of intercalation compounds, such as the intercalation of pyridine or its derivatives are slow and have limitations w.r.t. the yield obtained.[30,31,32]

2.2.3. Synthesis of ceramic products

Microwave processing of ceramic materials has reached a high degree of maturity. In ceramic production industry, the removal of solvent or moisture is a critical step in the generation of ceramic products. Initially, the use of microwaves was limited to the effective removal of solvents from solid samples. It is estimated that for materials with a water content below 5%, microwave drying is efficient than conventional drying methods. However, over the past few

3. Applications in Polymer Chemistry

Polymer chemistry, including ceramic processing, forms the single-largest application area of microwave chemistry. The use of polar reactants in polymerization reaction results in controlled synthesis and a combination of this with direct heating of reactants makes microwave heating an economically viable option. Curing is a polymerization process, which transforms a liquid resin to a solid, creating the maximum physical properties attainable from the materials. Using microwave radiation in curing has greatly increased the rate of the reactions. It has been found that the rate of a curing reaction, using microwaves, is not dependent on the power 35, 36 applied but on the way the pulse is applied. [33,34,35]

CONCLUSION:

microwave assisted organic synthesis has advantages over conventional technology: it is more energy efficient and it can lead to improved isolated yields of products. The advantages of this enabling technology have also been exploited in the context of multistep total synthesis and medicinal chemistry/drug discovery and have additionally penetrated related fields such as polymer synthesis, nanotechnology and biochemical processes. The obvious application of this approach to combinatorial synthesis should provide a major impetus for further developments in this area; a particularly important feature will be the continued development of microwave assisted solid phase reactions. The effects of microwave radiation on chemo-, regio- and stereo selectivity in synthesis and the continued quest for evidence of a non-thermal microwave effect are also important aspects which need to be addressed.

REFERENCES:

1. Krstenansky JL, Cotterill I. Recent advances in microwave-assisted organic syntheses. *Curr Opin Drug Discovery Dev* 2000; 4: 454–461
2. Gedye R, Smith F, Westaway K, et al. The use of microwave ovens for rapid organics synthesis. *Tetrahedron Lett* 1986; 27: 279–282.
3. Giguere RJ, Bray TL, Duncan SM, Majetich G. Application of commercial microwave ovens to organic synthesis. *Tetrahedron Lett* 1986; 27: 4945–4948.
4. Laporterie A, Marquié J, Dubac J. Microwave-assisted reactions on graphite in *Microwaves in Organic Synthesis*. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA; 2002: pp219-252.
5. Loupy A, Petit A, Hamelin J, Texier-Boullet F, Jacquault P, Mathe D. New solvent-free organic synthesis using focused microwaves. *Synthesis* 1998; 9:1213-1234.
6. Varma RS. The Chemistry of heterocycles: structure, reactions, syntheses, and applications. *Green Chem* 1999; 1: 43–55.
7. Bose AK, Banik BK, Lavlinskaia N, Jayaraman M, Manhas MS. More chemistry in a microwave. *Chemtech* 1997; 27: 18–24.
8. Bose AK, Manhas MS, Ganguly SN, Sharma AH, Banik BK. More chemistry for less pollution: Applications for process development. *Synthesis* 2002; 11;1578–1591.
9. Electromagnetic spectrum (microwave). Available from URL: <http://www.maotel.com>
10. Taylor M, Atri SS, Minhas S. Evaluate serve analysis: Developments in microwave chemistry. Available from: URL:www.rsc.org/images/evaluate/serve_tcm18-16758.pdf
11. Neas E, Collins M. Introduction to microwave sample preparation: Theory and practice. Washington: American Chemical Society; 1988: pp7-32.
12. Rajak H, Mishra P. Microwave assisted combinatorial chemistry: The potential approach for acceleration of drug discovery. *J Sci Indus Res* 2004; 63: 641-654.
13. Gabriel C, Gabriels S, Grant EH, Halstead BS, Mingos DMP. Dielectric parameters relevant to microwave dielectric heating. *Chem Soc Rev* 1998; 27: 213–223.
14. Mingos DMP, Baghurst DR. Applications of microwave dielectric heating effects to synthetic problems in chemistry. *Chem Soc Rev* 1991; 20: 1–47.
15. Strauss CR, Trainor RW. Developments in microwave assisted organic chemistry. *Aust J Chem* 1995; 48: 1665–1692.
16. Langa F, Cruz P, Hoz A, Ortiz A, Barra E. Microwave irradiation: more than just a method for accelerating reactions. *Contemp Org Synth* 1997; 4: 373–386.

17. Elander N, Jones JR, Lu SY, Stone-Elander S. Microwave-enhanced radiochemistry. *Chem Soc Rev* 2000; 29: 239–249.
18. Horeis AG, Pichler S, Stadler A, Gössler W, Kappe CO. Microwave-assisted organic synthesis—back to the roots. Fifth International Electronic Conference on Synthetic Organic Chemistry (ECSOC-5). Available from: URL: <http://www.mdpi.org/ecsoc-5.htm>, 1–30 September 2001.
19. Kappe CO, Dallinger D, and Murphree SS. Practical microwave synthesis for organic chemists: strategies, instruments, and protocols. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA; 2009.
20. Larhed M, Hallberg A. Microwave-assisted high-speed chemistry: a new technique in drug discovery. *Drug Discovery Today* 2001; 6: 406–416.
21. Gasgnier M, Loupy A, Petit A, Jullien H. New developments in the field of energy transfer by means of monomode microwaves for various oxides and hydroxides. *J Alloys Compd* 1994; 204: 165–72.
22. Lidström P, Tierney J, Wathey B, Westman J. Microwave-assisted organic synthesis—a review. *Tetrahedron* 2001; 57: 9225–9283.
23. Lew A, Krutzik PO, Hart ME, Chamberlin AR. Increasing rates of reaction: Microwave-assisted organic synthesis for combinatorial chemistry. *J Combinatorial Chem* 2002; 4: 95–105.
24. Loupy A, Perreux L. A tentative rationalization of microwave effects in organic synthesis according to the reaction medium and mechanistic considerations. *Tetrahedron* 2001; 57: 9199–9223.
25. Stadler A, Yousefi BH, Dallinger D, et al. Scalability of microwave-assisted organic synthesis. From single-mode to multimode parallel batch reactors. *Org Proc Res Dev* 2003; 7: 707–716.
26. Wilson NS, Sarko CR, Roth GP. Development and applications of a practical continuous flow microwave cell. *Org Proc Res Dev* 2004; 8: 535–538.
27. Ley SV, Baxendale IR. New tools and concepts for modern organic synthesis. *Nat Rev Drug Discovery* 2002; 1: 573–586.
28. Kappe CO. High-speed combinatorial synthesis utilizing microwave irradiation. *Curr Opin Chem Biol* 2002; 6: 314–320.
29. Schanche JS. Microwave synthesis solutions from personal chemistry. *Mol Diversity* 2003; 7: 293–300. www.personalchemistry.com;
30. Baghurst DR, Mingos DMP. Superheating effects associated with microwave dielectric heating. *J Chem Soc Chem Commun* 1992; 9: 674–677.
31. Glasnov TN, Kappe CO. Microwave-assisted synthesis under continuous-flow conditions. *Macromolecular Rapid Communications* 2007; 28(4): 395–410.
32. Qinhan J, Feng L, Hanqi Z, Liwei Z, Yanfu H, Daqian S. Applications of microwave techniques in analytical chemistry. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 1999; 18: 479–484.
33. Gupta M, Paul S, Gupta R. General characteristics and applications of microwaves in organic synthesis. *Acta Chim Slov* 2009; 56: 749–764.
34. Hargett WP. Sealing closure for high pressure vessels in microwave assisted chemistry. US Patent 6287526, 1999 Sep 20.
35. Berteaud AJ, Badot JC. High temperature microwave heating in refractory materials. *J Microwave Power* 1976; 11: 315–320.
36. Akyel C, Bilgen E. Microwave and radio-frequency curing of polymers: Energy requirements, cost and market penetration. *Energy* 1989; 14: 839–851.